

The upward mobility of recovery: Using lived experience to steer healing in the right direction

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There is undeniable mobility to recovery. Moving forward in your path to health and healing requires inertia. From the recovery rate, the sheer speed and velocity needed to push past life's setbacks and identify a sustainable pace is a feat that requires a high level of self-awareness and knowledge of one's diagnosis. Depending on the diagnosis, trauma history, and triggers, the individual will need to know how to lock on to a path that will lead them towards better health and avoid the undertow of relapse. This is a tightrope, and walking the line necessitates discipline, wisdom, and lived experience. To get right to the heart of the matter, unless therapists, peers, and mental health professionals practice techniques to help their consumers self-soothe and at greater peace with their situation to avoid havoc. Even worse, misapplication of therapeutic work can be just as disabling, if not more harmful, than dwelling or being upset. Of course, there is a fine line here before helpful becomes harmful. In the mental health realm, all too often, practitioners forget to be extra mindful not to cross this line and harm when it could have avoided with more practice. Researchers are hoping to explore this line and make it visible to the reader. The research is revealing that people practising this skill are too often clumsy in their approach. They sometimes work with limited information on how to correctly implement this skill in practice when providing therapy or peer-centric relationships. Depending on how these terms have been conceptualised from theory and applied to practice interventions, a small problem can turn into an even big problem.

Keywords: direction; health; lived experience; recovery; wellness

Finding the energy to move forward in recovery can be difficult. With severe symptoms, it can carry lethargy from medication side effects, or even worse, setbacks from poor decision-making from cognitive distortions that can form from delusional systems that can become fixed or solvent the condition (Acharya & Relojo, 2017). With all of these obstacles in your path to healing, finding the right course to avoid pitfalls can be problematic. Each successive setback can be even more demoralising. This is understandable but not a license to stop walking the path to health and healing.

While having a robust clinical prowess can help frame your weak points and strengths, only learning from lived experience will forecast how you will respond to stressors and how quickly you rally back from pitfalls and relapse risk (Deegan, 1988). Unfortunately, this means a period of trial and error. It does not sound very clinical, but it is very clinical, as testing and applied experiential knowledge are most certainly a part of the clinical picture. Sometimes, we need to see what works and what does not work before we can genuinely forecast the future from historical experiences. So how can we understand the mobility that moves our recovery along in better terms? Mobility is a movement. Above all, it is the energy that pushes us past holding patterns in our recovery in which people stagnate and feel trapped, without progress or Hope. These can be the most frustrating moments in our recovery when we do not seem to make any progress from week to week. Mobility makes progress possible. However, mobility itself is not progressing. It the mechanism that drives improvement forward (Guttman, 2017). It certainly seems to be for the camps in the mental health reform movement(s) – I have bracketed the ‘s’ because it is not one movement.

Defining help in clinical practice

Theoretically, all of us in mental health want the best for our fellow people suffering or in distress. Indeed, the climate in the rooms at mental health seminars, retreats, and the next team meeting at a local agency is never on the same page. Even when it comes down to our very intentions of helping other folks in distress, how to do so has become a bit nebulous lately in the field. This blip in the agreement between practitioners on best practices makes the helping process even more beguiling (Guttman, 2020). When can the helping profession not agree on what help means? Unfortunately, there is no consensus (not even close!) through care systems in Eurocentric expressions of mental health treatment or the reform movement because help is far too unique to the individual. We are working with people with different cross-sections of society. Moreover, even if we all did suffer from the same plight, the manifestation of any ‘disorder’ or symptom (for those that lean towards DSM-oriented frameworks for positing mental health issues as a constellation of illnesses requiring treatment) is going to be different. Even for folks on the other end of the spectrum (and it is just that, a spectrum of stances), understanding these issues at hand as a direct or indirect result of complex traumas or learned behaviours from environmental, discriminatory, or any number of nonorganic and codifying approaches to framing what the person needing makes it profoundly difficult to define the idea of help (Courtois, 2004). So, let us evaluate the different sides and various in-between areas of this spectrum of definitions intersecting help, mental health, and radical acceptance. We will begin with a small survey of symptoms in the medical model of mental health treatment. There are indisputably many diagnoses that have problematic symptoms. These symptoms complicate our social lives. Well, for starters, let us look at depressive symptoms. When someone is feeling sad, they may choose to isolate, among other possible behaviours. Now, evaluate this symptom of sadness as a case example. If we were to step inside the therapy room and observe this therapist practice radical acceptance, how might it approach? As a practicing therapist, this theoretical therapist could have several possible inroads to suggesting to his or her consumer that sometimes it is okay to be sad. A safe approach (for now, at least until it takes a dangerous turn, look out!) Sometimes, we all get upset; isn't this a given truth? This therapist might say that acceptance of our sadness, grief, or negative feelings and being all right with not being okay in the moment is also very encouraging. Sometimes this is true as well. To begin to understand this more, we first have to realise we have landed there.

Now, isolating is normal behaviour for many folks (maladaptive but normal) when we are sad. Well, a piece of accepting landing in a tough spot means possessing a level of self-awareness (Relojo & Gagani, 2016). Ask questions and check-in with the status of personal well-being (Ryff & Essex, 1992). A step forward, similar to enacting self-actualization, and self-awareness, are other insight-oriented cognitive processes that make us think more about our behaviour (Santos & Relojo, 2020). Now, here is the line. Just thinking about our actions does not mean we will choose to make healthy decisions and enact positive behaviours in the future (Slade, 2010). After all, at this point, sadness and knowing things are going well. Being more aware does not mean choosing to do the right thing in every situation. Holding on to the belief solving a problem is futile is an even bigger problem (Gagani et al., 2016). Therapists cannot gauge where people are in terms of the intensity of the symptom and its persistence/chronicity when it comes to patient safety. The risk of potential harm is even more dangerous. This is just one symptom in a giant galaxy of human behaviour where there are even more expressions and twice many outcomes depending on the contributing factors we discussed earlier. Now, this

writer thinks very highly of himself and his colleagues. Despite these lofty beliefs, this writer is also a realist and needs to be pragmatic at work as a therapist. Not even the most skilled and calculating clinician or peer can predict or calculate these outcomes (reading the DSM backward and forwards or as an expert in human behaviour) unless the therapist is supernaturally clairvoyant and can read into the future with their clinical gaze. For this very reason, there are always incidents in this line of work. Despite what we know, an element of unpredictability enmeshed into the very web of how we practice radical acceptance in therapy and during peer-centric relationships. Now, let us delve into more peer-centric interventions with the same need addressed: sadness, loneliness, or something similar (Bautista et al., 2018; Pilao et al., 2106). One great tested way of helping someone sad is not therapy or medication. Sometimes, it is just plain old-fashioned fun. Whether it is connecting with friends or feeling more connected to the community, socialisation is a great way to reduce sadness. Complete recovery or experiencing relief for people experiencing sadness can be establishing more meaningful friendships, time spent socialising, and having plain wholesome fun with peers. Now, that line that we talked about earlier is about to make its re-emergence into this conversation. Don't emotions like sadness sometimes make it more difficult to relate with others? When we feel sad, you do not necessarily want to get out there and take the world head-on? Maybe not. Peer relationships, friendships can suffer tremendous interpersonal failure in the wake of behaviours that are not prosocial. As a friend or a peer, how many figurative (hopefully not literal) slaps in the face with untoward behaviour will you take before dropping this disordered peer (or just plain rude and inhospitable)?

The peer relationship: Radical acceptance, mutuality, and support

Radical acceptance of a sad person's feeling comes with the peer's mutual responsibility to accept these persons where they are at with life, right? I mean, how can we practice mutuality and not be realistic about a sad person's potential behaviours when he or she does not feel well? Some friends may claim to be supportive. Some reality testing here. Let us be real if this were in the context of a job situation (Chavez et al., 2019). Even within family systems, some behaviours warrant immediate police intervention beyond a friend's support (Guttman, 2018). Threatening an ally and put them at risk of harm, this friend must call the authorities. There are so many symptoms that truly make prosocial interaction far too complex to practice radical acceptance without sitting on a vast litany of other interventions.

Knowing the craft will determine the practitioner's or peers' ability to identify this line and select an appropriate intervention congruent with a client's clinical picture's shifting nature. Increasingly tricky as old symptoms can manifest unpredictably. New ones may emerge during the recovery process as a direct or indirect result of those discussed earlier. Understanding this will go a long way in reducing possible resentment and anger from allies that may hold accountable for unexplainable behaviours or symptoms. Friends who understand these issues when practicing radical acceptance will always struggle with where the line is each time. When practising radical acceptance, making decisions about safety may not be mutual. Instead, how comfortable a friend is with active symptoms and how adequate friends obtain support (Caleb & Relojo, 2019). Sometimes, like all relationships, the decision will not always be mutual. Be prepared for that sobering possibility. There is no question that friends of someone carrying a mental health diagnosis deserve our unconditional radical acceptance of their symptoms and recovery journeys (Relojo-Howell, 2020). Unfortunately, be prepared for times when this may not always be possible due to the nature of so many things that can go wrong with our mental health.

Upward mobility: steering recovery in the right direction

Think of a car, and it is the engine. The engine moves the car along from point A to point B. However, depending on the driver's course and direction, the vehicle's journey can have several outcomes. The car can safely get to point B and experience movement towards its goal. The vehicle can crash on its way to point B and not make it to its destination. This is the stagnation, holding pattern, and deferred progress I was referring to, all of which depend on the knowledge, skills, wisdom, preparedness, and things that push back against relapse. As drivers in our recovery or captains of the ship, if you prefer that metaphor, we all need to steer apparent pitfalls. More importantly, we need to truly understand how far and how much we can push, continue moving forward in our recovery without burning out our engine, or worse, getting injured along the way. I have experienced many injuries and mishaps along the way to my path to health and healing. However, no harm so devastating that I could not keep moving forward. Why? Because I got to know my weak points very well. When I am collapsing, I learned to sit down and take a seat before hitting the hard-cold pavement of relapse and heartache: (a) learn your limits; (b) plan for the worst at all times; (c) know your weak points and nurture your strengths; (d) tally your victories and each marker or indicator you are making progress; (e) when you succeed, prepare to lose ground unless you get to know the mobility and momentum required to keep moving forward. Learning limits is a constant reminder of how far you can psychologically and physiologically push

your body before accumulating negative feedback or outcomes. Honestly, know that not being mindful of this can lead to the worst of relapses. Keeping in mind a great stretch is this awareness of your limits can be limitlessly fruitful in avoiding potentially harmful and challenging problems in your health path (Westerman, 2014). Keeping in mind, charting your victories, however small, is motivating but clinically helpful in raising your own awareness of what works and what does not move the momentum of healing along.

Lived experience as a self-diagnostic tool

The concept of recovery and healing is so complicated. Let us assume that people ‘heal’ as a by-product of their recovery, including many other aspects. These aspects include their overall stance on healing, approach to recovery, rate-of-recovery, and so many other nuances that contribute to our overall healing from trauma, self-inflicted harm, and organic brain disease. I would like to explore my own lived experience with first-onset psychosis.

I always knew the qualities of my personality were altered by schizophrenia. I approach problems differently today than before my disorder. I even come positive insertions into my life differently today. These insertions can be as simple as good conversation during the workday or meeting a new person and experiencing a budding relationship blossom. However, what exactly do I mean by different? The difference is at the level of how I handle such occurrences. These extend beyond the normal development of my personality, I believe. We all grow and mature over time. There is no question that some of the changes I am gesturing towards are due to my development's natural progression. However, I know myself better than that. I also know I have had to mature a lot faster than most people my age. This is mainly because, developmentally, I cannot afford to make the same mistakes people at my development stage make. Since my psychological landscape has little room for error, I need to be extra cautious, extra careful, and speedy in how I go about maturing and the maturation process. I need to handle things differently (Christensen & Mikkelsen, 2008). However, my question is: how much of this is a by-product of the changes due to the first onset? I genuinely wonder if the resultant changes that manifested in my brain necessitated me to handle things differently. Meaning, because my mind now functions differently, is the need to feel things differently from the first onset, or is it a result of how my brain went about healing? Are the changes the direct result of trauma to the brain or the development of my mind healing ‘normally’? I will tell you one thing. For the most part, I have not changed how I handle things because I wanted to be spontaneous and change things. No, I have had to because, after the first onset, I was so disordered that I could not speak intelligibly enough for others to gather anything meaningful from my speech. I have written extensively on stilted language and the changes during my episode when the first onset first hit my brain's synapses. However, I rarely evaluate how my speech was before my disorder and after my recovery. More importantly, given my findings, how I find my own brain's capacity to heal from psychosis? I am no speech analyst. In truth, my expertise is in rhetoric and only helpful when studying the words used, delivery, style, memory, and delivery. However, even with my limited knowledge of how rhetoric works. A side-by-side comparison of my speech and ability to communicate before the first onset and after is bothersome on many levels and remarkably telling on others. Incredibly speaking of the energy, I invested in my recovery, the specific skills I was able to relearn, and how far I could push forward in areas that benefited from relearning how to speak and communicate. That is to say, not every aspect of my rhetorical canon was repaired or responded to the work I invested in regaining my language facilities.

In my 2006 radio show, *County Speak*, on WHRW 90.5 Binghamton, I was at the height of my college speaking career. Thoroughly before any schizophrenia symptoms, I was in complete command of what I wanted to say and how I went about saying it. After listening to the show alongside a recent interview from this year, I was taken aback. I sounded like an altogether different person years ago. Let us break it down on the level of rhetoric. In terms of style, my speech was certainly more spontaneous in 2007, with less effort and energy expended on my part to seem so. My memory was remarkably better in 2007. I needed to pause less to gather my thoughts, and the flow and diction were more even and smooth. All these aspects of rhetoric have taken a turn after the first onset. These aspects of my speech responded well to the effort and energy I invested in my treatment targeting my language. However, they did not reconstitute completely and heal up without a hardened scab and layer of nonfunction or impairment, still visible to this day. Only on the level of delivery have I been able to learn how to be more impactful. This has nothing to do with my illness, however. This harkens back to what I was speaking about earlier. That I have had to invest a ton of energy into the process, and my delivery, how I capture my audience's attention, keep it, and redirect my life's sheer inertia into the work is clear as day and uncontested. I cannot help but cite the greatest, Mohammad Ali, who was not as fast on his feet as he once was after returning to boxing after years of political exile. He learned to lean on the ropes with the famous icon ‘rope-a-dope’ strategy and outpace his challengers with the imposition of will and his unrivalled stamina. While I am not as savvy with my ability to choose words as quickly and effectively or speak smoothly and spontaneously, I have learned to lean on my energy. My sheer will to rise above my impairment

is genuinely the main asset I have in my corner. Sure, identifying my weaknesses and pinpointing what works and what has not along the way was also important. However, indeed, my energy and the level of intensity I put into the work ahead is what continues to drive my healing forward.

Plan B: relapse and reconstitution

The anxiety of a small problem has the potential to eat us alive. Imagine the stress around a significant mental illness and lifelong disorder? Like most thoughts surrounding fear, paranoia, and anxious thinking, they all snowball, combining and multiplying our worst thoughts. Following my self-care plan across the lifespan will mean living a life free of this fear; or at least regulated as best as possible to reduce the likelihood and chances of paranoia and the fear that we will see one day relapse or become sick without warning. This would pose to be quite tricky. With such a connected group of friends, some angry with me, others sitting on the fence, and some with a mouth so big, and any sort of help usually backfired on all of us. My biggest concern was always to position myself the right way. With friends, providers, and co-workers, I learned to do this well. In doing so, I allied with my therapist, treatment team, and close peers with a vested interest in my mental health. I firmly believe in the importance of establishing a deep trust with close personal everyday contacts. In doing so, if my collaterals begin to detect an extreme and toxic abnormality in my health, I felt safe enough to take their advice and concerns seriously. Sure, no clinician or friend can get a perfect read on our health. However, for those of us without a great deal of self-awareness or drive to look after ourselves, there are still options and strategies to stay healthy without relying entirely on your own devices (Clare, 2003). Such is the case for people like my friend and others I would encounter along my healing path.

Indeed, not everyone cares enough about their health to self-monitor all the time. In other cases, the day's priority will capture our attention; for example, paying the rent, housing, employment, or even just showing up to work on time. If not also addressed in our lives, all of these would disrupt our mental health and even jeopardise our lives regardless of our diagnosis. Staying connected with collaterals to delegate health needs is a great 'Plan B' when your self-care takes a back seat to life's priorities (which only seem like they come before focusing on maintaining or working toward good mental health). During the first few years out of the hospital, I provided regular, almost weekly reports to my friends regarding my treatment status and medication changes. This served multiple purposes: (a) kept me firmly treatment focused; (b) communicating my treatment needs to other people; and (c) allowed my friends to get a better idea of where I was at, so they could be as attentive as possible with my needs on a moment-by-moment basis. Avoiding or reducing the risk of relapse does not mean handing out your mental health's full responsibility to others. Instead, as a prosumer, I recommend you hand part of it to family, friends, and those you trust to keep them looped into your clinical treatment (Ritzer et al., 2012). These natural supports are excellent advice sources even when we may disagree with their reasoning (unless it puts us directly or indirectly at risk of harm). I am suggesting that regardless of how we feel or think about the validity of our friends' opinions on our mental status, our disorder disrupts our capacity to stay connected to reality. This may take the form of elaborate delusions about our life, which complicate our own interpretive eye's ability to know what is truly happening with our health.

In the end, anyway, people want to manage their mental health is a significant step but do at least that much. Have a plan and have another goal when the original roadmap to better health becomes unworkable. Ultimately, whether you have a chronic condition or an acute diagnosis, relapse is only to be feared when you are not doing what you need to do to work toward better health and healing. Relapsing and experiencing the renewal of old symptoms can still remind you to get back on track with your recovery. Keep going, and do not stop. When you stop taking care of yourself, be prepared for your worst fears not just to haunt you but become the grim reality you feared so vehemently instead of investing the same mental energy in health and healing.

In my opinion, as a prosumer, the best part of recovery is gaining access to new responsibilities, materials, information, and all the good things that come with stable living. Given that relapse is an inevitable part of recovery, the loss of materials, access, and resources attributed to relapsing and mental status degradation is the worst part of relapsing, in my opinion. Usually, the biggest loser in a person's life relapsing is hygiene, and on a broader level, the person's living environment or home. It may be a matter of neglecting cleaning or not being aware of dirt and disorganisation in the house, or it may go even more profound. I even treated a former psychiatrist in his home, providing him psychotherapy. Sadly, I watched this psychiatrist lose ground weekly on my watch, knowing full well what was happening. He was decompensating rapidly. For this man, this means a growing delusional system and potentially aggressive behaviour, according to his case history. While he was never free of his delusions, earlier on, the distortions were much less fixed and pronounced in what he was reporting to our team in session. According to him, he was set up' by extra-governmental agents and was in his position because he was the target of a more massive governmental conspiracy. This conspiracy was becoming more problematic for the psychiatrist, and ultimately, he became so agitated in session and

adversarial that all treatment failed (Malcolm, 1986). When our team returned, we came back with the local police. With the shield's help, police entered the apartment against the psychiatrist's will, sitting him down on his couch, handcuffed. On the sofa, he was sitting upright, screaming utter nonsense and profanities and the police. This was hard to watch both as a provider and as a person with lived experience. Someone who knows what it is like to be handcuffed amid a delusional rage. Sadly, I have also witnessed police storming doorways with shields to access a home fortified for the 'end' to avoid being evicted. Barricading yourself in the home or something even worse is never the answer. It may even further your risk of relapsing more acutely – if you go against police orders or personnel, it will only exaggerate your problems and complicate your relapse even more deeply. The worst privilege to lose during relapse is the freedom of healthy living. With healthy living comes life circumstances that support wellness and mental hygiene (Pilao et al., 2017).

There is no question that when we lose healthy living practices, we lose the freedom to be useful to our bodies and minds and treat ourselves kindly and with respect at all times. Relapsing means surrendering some of these healthy moments for symptomatic periods of distress in which it is more difficult to live peaceably with the world at large and adjust to our situations accordingly. Relapse ages the body. During my many meals with Caroline, I would just gaze at her face. She looked tired all the time. Sadly, she aged twenty years in a span of ten. She was no stranger to the police and emergency service intervention. 'I climbed into the city fountains wearing all white robes and began cutting myself. The fountains turned red. It was a horrific scene that I thought was directly from the Bible. The end of time,' my friend would recant. I would try to tell people in similar shoes as my friend about my injection and how much I preferred getting medication administered through my muscle tissue so I would not have to take medication daily, just once a month for the shot. I explained the benefits and tried to seem like an expert. She would consider speaking to her doctor about it. I was an expert, but my friend always knew better yet was still wrong about the following steps to take in her recovery.

For people living in a group home or apartment treatment facility, relapse usually brings with it more concrete freedoms that may be stripped away. Sometimes, relapsing means changes in curfew or even may trigger reduced independence in the community; doors to your residence that are usually open for residents to come freely may become restricted. Such is the case of people like my friend. She has to 'pack' her medication. Every few days, in front of the agency personal, before transporting her meds back to her apartment in the community, my friend has to provide visible proof she had medication on hand. In cases like hers, this might also mean increased home visits, if the person is living on their own, or added chores in the community home of a residence if they live in an adult home or community residence. Relapse can mean many things (Frank, 2007). It can also mean losing mental health housing or moving into a residence with more supervision and more restrictions on your freedoms. In any event, be mindful of what the losses mean for the bigger picture. Ultimately, what matters is your pathway back to health and wellness.

Dislodging fear from self-disclosure: communication, authenticity, and healing

In most cases, like most of us in the social and professional world, I am communicating a message learned from lived experience, sometimes understood, from observation, other times from research, as well as experiential knowledge. Regardless of the signal or role I am in or hat I am wearing in my job or professional work (Kuha et al., 2018), or a friend I am speaking with, I am communicating an important message. In most cases, the message is received, and we get feedback. Sometimes people will like what we have to say, and other times, people will disagree. How we signal, that is, send the message, depends on our skills as communicators. While everyone processes the same content differently, it is in our hands as communicators, regardless of the hats we wear, to communicate the message in a manner in which people will understand it. The person may disagree with the statement, but if we genuinely prioritise the act of communication over the importance of the reception of the message, we take one giant leap closer to getting over our own self-importance in our interpersonal landscapes. This includes our jobs, our social circles, and all things involving interacting with people.

In a world where diversity can sometimes be a scarcity, there is no reason to take further steps in limiting our ability to reach people. In my profession, particularly the helping field, and for all of us that enjoy time spent in others' companies, there is an unspoken fear that the person we are speaking to will not listen or is not listening. Even worse, we perhaps fear the listener, client, or friend will dislike us because of what we say. However, I am suggesting that this fear is misplaced. If you are fearful of people disliking you because of what you have to say, think again. There is no such thing as a misuse of self-disclosure or the act of revealing your history to other people. Instead, there is only the possibility of miscommunication. I mean that the fear of people knowing more about you, at least in my opinion, should not be the priority in the helping profession; instead, the fear of not signalling or sending the right message needs to be the concern. Why? In a world of

increasing tragedy and unfortunate circumstances, we should be out there, helping people learn from our lived experiences. Instead, helpers, friends, family, and everyone are more concerned with people's judgments and biases that we lose sight of our mission to share the message. People do not have to agree or like you, but sharing the news is more important if they are listening. With this said, prioritising the message's clarity needs to be the primary concern for people in the helping profession. No question sharing the news and communicating it the right way needs to be what has been doted upon by helpers if help is, in fact, the primary goal of what we are setting out to do. Instead, our fear takes over, and we put these self-imposed limits on our communication that we feel people will respect more. I suggest that if people appreciate you, authenticity, honesty, and candidness are better qualities than just telling people what they want or what you think they should hear. In the helping profession, where authenticity is also scarce and needs to be a commodity, we are doing others a disservice to learn from our lived experience (Pinto-Coelho & Relojo, 2017). What baffles me is that there are so many peers, people with lived experience, and those carrying a diagnosis uncomfortable with their lived experience. These are peers that limit and self-imposed boundaries around what they share about their history, depending on the hat they are wearing and how the person is communicating with might perhaps appreciate what they have to say (Iannarino, 2018). I just want to say people appreciate honesty. People appreciate candidness, not artificiality or assumptions of their particular likes and dislikes. This is why my head spins when I discover, after speaking with other peers, friends, family, and all those involved with the helping process, a common fear of sharing particular aspects of their past. This is not to say that everything is relevant to disclose or if the person listening will benefit. Still, the fear or primary concern of the person sharing should constantly be communicating their history accurately and effectively for the person listening to have the opportunity to benefit from it. If you are a peer who has genuinely recovered, in recovery, or a person interested in having people benefit from your life's lessons, then who cares if the person listening does not like you or what you have to say. Not only did you put that person you shared your history with in a better position to begin learning from your lived experience, but you also included them in your path to healing. The very act of having your peer, friend, or family member in your approach to recovery is healing. Including your peer in your path to healing is not just healing in and of itself. It is a simple step further in the way to sustainable recovery. Indeed, recovery and our belief in experiencing positive change in our lives need to be authentic and real if we begin and stay healed. The omission of truth is a disservice to peers and those that run the risk of making the same mistakes. Share feel free to disclose all aspects of your lived experience and mental health history. The moment we begin limiting the self-disclosed lessons, we genuinely put a roadblock on communication and the possibility of people learning from our lived experience.

Recovery as a privilege: Passing through the intersections of healing and wellness

I have been privileged in my recovery in many ways. There are many forms of privilege people can 'benefit' from, most of the time, at others' expense. During my recovery, I have benefited from the financial, emotional, cultural, and intellectual prowess to move forward in my healing & wellness without bounds. I will make these aspects of privilege, which, without question, intersect recovery, visible to you, the reader, to challenge those that believe anyone can heal from their illness (Relojo et al., 2015). I cannot help but share a moment of the first internship in social work to shed more light on recovery as a privilege. During that time, I was interning in an end-of-life unit in a regional cancer centre. Every morning, I attended nursing rounds, in which a report was given to the incoming day shift. It was at that time when I first heard the term: 're-hab-able' as in, he or she is too ridden with cancer, he is not rehab-able. This concept shocked me deeply. Perhaps it surprised me because I was embarking on a recovery-based learning trajectory, or because, personally & professionally, I have always believed that no one is beyond repair. Slowly, I learned not everyone shared in my philosophy of recovery. The very web of meaning surrounding recovery & healing is encircling and intersects with privilege. As time unfolded, I would learn more about the intersectionality of opportunity and improvement in mental health and other related fields (Relojo, 2018). The following learning moment came during my work as a Recovery Specialist working for the Mental Health Association. I was a field worker in the inner city of Yonkers, New York. During my career as a peer with one client, I would run into a stumbling block whenever I met with this individual. The client would remind me, during my motivational talks, that I have a family, and, in turn, there was a reason I was more successful in my recovery than the other people on my caseload. Looking back on that experience, I cannot help but remember feeling the metaphorical frog in my throat every time this client reminded me that my family was the reason, I was so successful in my recovery.

There is no question that our supports are crucial in our healing. In terms of healing, only some people have a family with a vested interest in their recovery. Not everyone recovering from a significant mental health diagnosis has a family willing to take on the challenges of supporting someone they love carrying on the fight against mental illness. The layers of privilege go deeper than just family support. There is emotional support from friends, professionals. Financial aid to carrying on payment for new medications or housing when the disruptions of symptoms take on forms that cause property loss, either from self-destruction or misplacement

of goods due to memory loss & confusion. Even down to transportation to and from treatment, this all costs money and resources that are not available to everyone carrying a mental health diagnosis. Even more profound are the cultural implications of privilege. Many cultures do not believe in diagnosis. They do not see mental health as something that requires treatment or medical intervention upon dysregulation. I am lucky that I come from a background in which my heritage does not interfere with me getting the mental health treatment I required from my early adulthood and recovery from schizophrenia. Some cultures do not view people exhibiting symptoms from a mental health diagnosis as requiring necessary medical or psychiatric intervention, which may be lifesaving or life-preserving. Ultimately, I have been privileged to live out my existence in a manner in which my friends, family, financial status, and cultural background have all been critical players in hurling me closer to my healing & recovery. Many people continue to struggle without the necessary resources they need to keep moving forward in their journey carrying a mental health diagnosis. So, when you encounter people in your life that need help: reach out to them. Point them towards the necessary resources they will need to continue living without bounds. Privilege them with your helping hands and walk alongside them in their recovery.

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